

Preventive Study Of Aerosol-Solar Radiation In The Industrial Zone of Yopougon By 2050

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Abstract: This study was carried out to identify environmental problems linked to the concentration of air pollutants. The objective was to show the impacts of industrial waste within the Yopougon industrial site by 2050. The remote sensing methods adopted are based on satellite images with high spatial resolution. The Sentinel-2 data acquired was used for modeling aerosol-solar radiation. The results obtained are forecast maps which have been interpreted in this article. The evaluated thermality is between +10 and 100 w.m⁻² over a period of 30 years. A spatial analysis made it possible to spread the distribution of contaminated air intended for breathing and the aggravated degradation of the environment located in the factories, including its surrounding neighborhoods.

Keywords : Solar radiation, Aerosol, Remote sensing, Cartography, Abidjan-Ivory Coast.

RESUME

La présente étude a été réalisée afin de cerner les problèmes environnementaux liés à la concentration des polluants atmosphériques. L'objectif était de montrer les impacts des déchets industriels au sein du site industriel de Yopougon à l'horizon 2050. Les méthodes de télédétection adoptées sont basées sur les images satellitaires à haute résolution spatiale. Les données de Sentinel-2 acquises ont servi à la modélisation des radiations aérosol-solaire. Les résultats obtenus sont des cartes de prévisions qui ont été interprétées dans cet article. La thermicité évaluée est comprise entre +10 et 100 w.m⁻² sur une période de 30 ans. Une analyse spatiale a permis d'étaler la distribution d'air contaminé destiné à la respiration et la dégradation aggravée de l'environnement implanté des usines, y compris ses quartiers environnants.

Mots clés : Radiation solaire, Aérosols, Télédétection, Cartographie, Abidjan-Côte d'Ivoire.

INTRODUCTION

The prevention of aerosol-solar radiation risks exceeds the predictions of environmental impacts made in the case of climate change. The study was carried out within the industrial zone of Yopougon, including its surrounding districts. In addition, it is precisely the oldest among the five zones in the Abidjan district. It is currently facing very dense urban sprawl with numerous homes. The environment is therefore subject to strong demographic pressure. The area is perfectly vulnerable to the risk of thermal and atmospheric pollution with the exposure of the population to toxic pollutants in contaminated air. Due to the numerous industrial wastes (solid, liquid and gas) which are produced and rejected by the factories installed in the study site. Of course, the new area is not taken into account because it is uninhabited and the human stake is very low or almost non-existent.

The issue presented in this study is the deterioration of air quality and its impact on the environment. In the face of a growing population, it is undeniable to question the impact of aerosols in the air and the environment. The general objective of this study is to assess the level of air and environmental degradation. Specifically, these are:

- quantify aerosol-solar radiation
- model the concentration of aerosols and the solar radiative surface
- map aerosol-solar radiation

This study is structured into three axes. The first focuses on the presentation of the study area. The second sets out the material and methods. The third revolves around the results and the discussion.

1. Presentation of the study site

The Yopougon industrial zone which is the subject of this study is located between 5°20' and 5°34.10' north longitude and between 4°20' and 4°03.77' west latitude in the boreal hemisphere (figure 1). There are currently two sites which constitute the Yopougon industrial zone. The former industrial site is located in the municipality of Yopougon. The new industrial site is in Attinguié on the northern highway at the exit of the city of Abidjan.

Figure 1 : Study site location map

2. Materials

2.1. Data

In the case of this study, the scenes are taken during the dry and rainy periods of 2019, 2020 and 2021. They have been uploaded to the Copernicus platform (www.sentinel.copernicus.eu). All the images used were obtained in the descending phase. They were acquired using the Datum projection system. The optimal choice of bands was carried out according to the objectives set by this study. For processing satellite data, the characteristics of the atmospheric bands are recorded in the following table. Table I summarizes the characteristics of Sentinel-2 bands used for the treatment of atmospheric pollutants. The band properties were taken into account in the optimal choice of each atmospheric band (B1, B9, B10). In addition, the data layers of the urban grid constitute all of the digital information which is associated with satellite information.

Table I : Characteristics of Sentinel-2 strips for the treatment of atmospheric pollutants

Bands	Spatial resolution (m)	Channel (nm)	Wavelength	Property
B1-Aerosol	60	443		Detect aerosol
B10- Cirrus	60	1400		Detect aerosol-icloud
B9- H ₂ O	60	945		Reporting attendance Water

Infrared bands were the digital data required for the spatialization of thermal pollutants. They are illustrated in Table II.

Table II : Characteristics of Sentinel-2 bands for thermal pollutant mapping

Bands	Spatial resolution (m)	Channel (nm)	Wavelength	Propriétés
B7 : Near-infrared	20	600		Detect of change heat
B8a : Medium infrared	20	750		Detect of change heat
B8 : Medium infrared	10	900		Detect of change heat

2.2. Work materials

The carrying out of this work favored the use and exploitation of a set of equipment according to the methodology adopted.

2.2.1. Data collection equipment

Data collection equipment is listed below :

- GNSS receiver, Garmin Etrex 30X for sampling bitter points during field campaigns, the margin of error of which is between 0.5 m and 2 m ;
- field data collection technical sheet.

2.2.2. Data Processing Equipment

The data processing equipment consists of a MacBook Pro computer and a COMPAQ laptop on which software is installed to process all the digital data. All software is detailed in the next section.

2.2.3. Software

Software for data collection and processing is shown below :

- Excel 2016, Word 2016 for processing attribute tables and texts ;
- ArcGIS 10.2 for the extraction of bitter points, geoprocessing and creation of the area aerosol-solar radiation ;
- Qgis 2.18 to convert OSM files to Shapefile, spatial analysis and cartographic production ;
- Snap 6.0 for processing Sentinel-2 data ;
- Zotero for online documentary research and for listing bibliographical references ;
- Idrisi for modeling aerosol images based on the Markov chain.

3. Methods

3.1. Satellite data acquisition

The choice of dates relates to the three years of study 2019, 2020 and 2021 over which the field campaigns were carried out in order to obtain recent and updated data. These data were acquired to be used in aerosol modeling and to predict future aerosol-solar radiation by 2050. All of the images were acquired with a top-

down view on the website of the European Space Agency (ESA) Sentinel-2 provided 13 multispectral bands, 6 of which were used in the processing carried out.

3.2. Vector data layer collection

The field campaigns made it possible to collect bitter points of thermal and atmospheric pollution sources within the study area. The urban grid was acquired from the Bbbike cartographic database (www.extract.Bbbike.org). The metric coordinates are in OSM format (OpenStreetMap) and the urban grid is in shapefile extension (shp).

3.3. Data treatment

3.3.1. Processing of data layers

The GPX data were extracted with arctoolbox under ArcGIS 10.2. The urban grid was processed with QGIS 2.18. All vector layers have been converted into a shapefile. They were then transferred into the databas.

3.3.2. Processing of satellite images

3.3.2.1. Atmospheric treatment

Air pollution treatment is carried out assuming that the environment is uniform. The environmental effect correction (Ee) is applied to a set of three atmospheric (B1, B9, B10) and infrared (B8, B8a, B7) bands with the Sen2cor algorithm under Snap. Surface reflectance is obtained under the uniform assumption noted :

Equation (1)

$$Ee = \rho s.unif$$

Calculations of environmental reflectance per pixel (ρ_{pixel}) :

$$\rho_{pixel} = \rho s.env$$

Equation (2)

A first Gaussian convolution filter is carried out in order to calculate a weighted average of the surrounding reflectance. Strictly, it should depend on the quantity of aerosols present in the atmosphere. This means that the less aerosols there are, the more radiation appears sufficiently large. A second constant 3x3 median filter is applied to the different image processing without deterioration of the latter. Sure, it improves the contrast of filtered images.

Surface reflectance is shown by the formula (HAGOLLE, 2016) :

$$\rho s = [\rho s.unif.T \uparrow \cdot (1 - \rho s.unif . S / 1 - \rho s.env^s) - \rho s.env.T \uparrow_{dif}] / T \uparrow_{dir}$$

Equation (3)

This equation is the total rising surface reflectance, sum of the diffuse (Tdif) and direct (Tdir) atmospheric transmission. S is the atmospheric albedo of approximately 0,3. All quantities are deduced from radiative transfer calculations and depend on the amount and type of aerosols. The Sen2cor correction is evidenced by the quality of the output image, among other things by the number of corrected pixels, with 1800 by 1800 pixels. All the pixels of the matrix cover the area of interest subject to study (the industrial site), including its surrounding districts.

3.3.2.2. Extraction from study site

The extraction of the study site is carried out from a mask on all of the processed digital images. The boundary of the study site was the necessary data to carry out this operation. Nevertheless, some bitter points are used to extract aerosol images.

The extraction operation is performed on all the processed data.

3.3.2.3. Estimation of radiative forcing of aerosols

The radiative forcing of aerosols is calculated with the difference in net radiative flux resulting from the presence of aerosols. It can be quantified at the top of the atmosphere, at low altitude or at the ground surface, according to equation (4) (TAHIRI *et al*, 2012 ; CHAUVIGNE, 2016):

$$\Delta F_z = (F_{\uparrow} - F_{\downarrow}) - (F_{\uparrow 0} - F_{\downarrow 0})$$

Equation (4)

Equation (4) distinguished the upward flux $F_{\uparrow}$ (aerosol + infrared) and the flux $F_{\downarrow}$ (aerosol + infrared) downward. The indices ($\uparrow 0$) and ($\downarrow 0$) correspond to the fluxes calculated with very few aerosols, very clear skies or aerosol-cloud for a hazy sky. F_z is expressed $W.m^{-2}$. In the standard, the maximum and minimum surface reflectance obtained in the statistical matrix of the aerosol-infrared bands is used in the previous equation.

3.3.2.4. Method of spatial representation of air pollution prevention over 30 years

This method is based on cartographic processing, the first phase of which consists of importing aerosol images into Idrisi software. The Markov chain is applied on image data. The input parameters are inserted with the aim of obtaining a good agreement of the forecasts on the aerosol image models. In the second phase, aerosol images modeled with Idrisi are sent to ArcGIS 10.2. The aera solar radiation tool is placed on the modeled aerosol images. Notwithstanding, it is used to carry out spatial analysis by combining the radiative forcing of aerosols with the solar radiation surface in relation to the concentration of aerosols present on the site studied. This operation is very convenient for a visual analysis of the acquired results.

Other data (landmarks, urban grid, road, islands) from the field campaigns are inserted into the matrix in order to improve the models of aerosol radiative surfaces. All information integrated into the models comes from previous aerosol treatments carried out. Input parameters are entered for each processed image. All these parameters were duly controlled in order to minimize or eliminate biases from the expected radiative forcing results. They are defined for the periods of 2031, 2041 and 2051. Thus, the atmospheric pollutant prevention maps are produced from aerosol images modeled over a 30 year.

All of the parameters provided are illustrated in figure (2) (below).

Figure 2 : Area solar radiation and aerosol parameters ; Period : (a) 2031 ; (b) 2041 ; (c) 2051.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Atmospheric aerosol radiative forcing

Table III summarizes the analysis results of aerosol radiative forcing from 2019 to 2021. The analysis of air pollutant emissions is followed by the radiative assessment produced by the aerosol population at the top of the atmosphere, in the lower atmospheric layer as well as on the terrestrial surface (soil).

Tableau III : Radiative forcing of aerosols from 2019 to 2021

Year	F↑ aerosol + ifr	F↓ aerosol + ifr	RFA (W.m ⁻²)
2019	230,509	102,0087	-139,49
2020	231,4874	87,678	-122,19
2021	227,7575	61,0061	-90,24

Aerosol radiative forcing indicates warming during the day and cooling at night in the earth-atmosphere system. It depends strongly on the surface albedo and that of fine and ultrafine aerosol particles. The values for the locality studied record a variation from -139,49 W/m² to -90,24 W/m² which relatively corresponds to a weak contribution in the direction of cooling of the earth-atmosphere system. The representation of the forcing as a function of the albedo shows a linear trend with an ascending and descending flow, reflecting the reliability of the results of analysis of atmospheric pollution. Aerosol-infrared fluxes of the ascending and descending order are weak, describing a forcing with an aerosol radiation of -90,24 W/m² in 2021. There is normally the formation of radio elements with irradiation of non-elements. However, warming is more intense during the day and very slow during the night. The set of aerosol-infrared fluxes characterized by an ascending and descending direction shows a fluctuation from -139,49 W/m² to -122,19 W/m² between 2019 and 2020. The cooling is more rapid at night in 2019 and 2020 compared to 2021 which is slow. Radiative forcing influences the intensity of sunlight due to the types of waste in fine and ultrafine particles observed locally within the industrial site and its surroundings. The infrared transmittance due to the aerosol increases with visibility. This is due to the decrease in the optical thickness. When optical thickness appears clearly, the fluxes vary simultaneously. So, transmittance depends on wind speed and aerosol type. Fine and ultrafine aerosols play a significant role in the radiation balance of the atmosphere and air pollution. The chemical composition of fine and ultrafine aerosols is a crucial factor for understanding these impacts. It is also essential to model air pollution more precisely in the context of looking for potential sources at the local scale. All illustrations are described in figure (3).

Figure 3 : Flow of FRA from 2019 to 2021 ; upward flow aerosol + infrared (ifr) in blue ; downward flow aerosol + infrared (ifr) in red.

4.2. Aerosol-solar radiation mapping for 2050

The maps show the concentration of aerosols and solar radiation in 2031, 2041 and 2051. They are forecast and projection maps for the exposure of atmospheric pollutants.

Figure (4) spatializes the aerosol concentration combined with the solar radiation of 2031.

Figure 4 : Aerosol-solar radiation mapping of 2031

Figure (6) (below) shows the spatial distribution of aerosol layers and radiative surface within the industrial environment in 2051.

Figure 6 : Aerosol-solar radiation mapping of 2051

The aerosol-solar radiative surface marks a growth of +20 to +100 w/m² which extends from north to south and from east to west of the area. It is medium with +20 w/m², very high from +50 w/m² and becomes very extreme with an index of +100 w/m². The explosive increase in radiative forcing that combines with solar radiation could result in catastrophe. The days and nights would regularly be marked by very hot heat. The incessant thermal rise would cause heatwaves. Cooling is therefore non-existent. Thermal instabilities remain priceless. The effect of heat is exacerbating and would be very harmful to the future population. Thermal pollution increases suddenly and becomes unbearable for the resident population near polluted sites. The direct impact of aerosols would result in the direct attenuation or intensification of solar or telluric radiation by diffusion or gaseous absorption. Scattering or absorption depends on the physical and optical properties of

the aerosols, their chemical composition and the wavelength of the radiation. The analysis is justified by sources of ground emissions and the interaction of the aerosol population with the atmosphere. Indeed, certain atomic compound lose their mass by emitting particles or electromagnetic radiation, which accentuates warming in space confinement. Furthermore, the ground would have cracks in places under the high heat due to intense radioactivation. There would be dry fog throughout the day and even during the night. In short, the maps show the forecast of the level of risk of propagation of aerosol particles of fine and ultrafine sizes. They understand exposure to radiative effects and the impacts of surface heating within the industrial zone, including its surrounding neighborhoods.

Discussion

Pollution risk prevention cards and the spread of atmospheric waste have succeeded in preventing solar radiation from aerosols. The projection was made over 30 years ranging from 2031, 2041 and 2051. Exposure to radiation would be harmful to the future resident population surrounding the industrialized zone. Strictly speaking, values of +10 to +100 w.m^{-2} make it possible to predict extreme pollution from fine and ultrafine aerosols of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_1 and $\text{PM}_{0.1}$ types. The pollutants concerned are dispersed throughout the study area. This forecast is coherent because it exceeds the radiative effect of the chemical compounds which impact the layers of the lower atmosphere. It use information from aerosol maps, taking into account border conditions (road, buildings, etc.) and weather conditions. Therefore, it could have heatwave episodes and serious health disasters. These results differ from those acquired in the research of FOUCHER *et al* (2017) which does not mention any prediction.

Conclusion

The study presented in this manuscript takes place in the context of climate change. The objective set by this study was to evaluate the level of degradation of thermal and atmospheric pollution within the industrial site and its surroundings by 2050. The site subject to the field missions is currently an industrialized urban area with strong demographic pressure. The methods are based on digital data from Sentinel-2 at high spatial resolution. These data were collected and then processed to obtain solar radiation prediction models. In addition, a spatial analysis was applied to the acquired models. Atmospheric waste prevention maps aim to prevent increased aerosol radiative forcing that materializes at the ground surface. Aerosol-solar radiation was evaluated for values between +10 w/m^2 and +100 w/m^2 from 2031 to 2051. Consequently, the thermal rise is high and remains very worrying. It could have very harmful consequences for the future population. The difficulties of this study result from the inaccessibility of certain areas of the industrial site due to security services and/or the extent of thermal exposure.

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